

Assessment of the National Orientation Agency Public Relations Roles in Sensitising the Public during Key National Issues in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Roles of National Orientation Agency (NOA) in sensitising the Public and examined the purpose of the agency in line with visibility of their actions during the Key National Issues in Osun State. Survey research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised all the 18, 653 civil servants in the State of Osun out of which a sample size of 810 respondents was selected using multistage sampling procedure. A self-developed questionnaire was used to collect data. The test items reliability coefficients were 0.83, 0.90 and 0.79 respectively using Cronbach's alpha respectively. Data were analysed using descriptive. Only 74% of the respondents described NOA as ineffective in terms of enlightening the populace about Nigeria key National Issues; the potency of all the media of communication were underutilised Mean ≤ 2.49 with attending apathy of the populace towards whatever information received from NOA. The research concluded that NOA is ineffective in terms of carrying out its function properly and efficiently as respondents' casted vote of no confidence on her which led to apathy on the part of the respondents towards whatever instruction, information or directives dished out by the agency. The study, therefore recommended that NOA needs to improve and adopt a sound public relations strategies in redeeming its image and ensuring that a mutually beneficial relationship is built and sustained with the public.

Keywords: Key national issues, National Orientation Agency (NOA), COVID-19, Police brutality and insecurity

Introduction

The National Orientation Agency (NOA) was established in Nigeria by Decree 100 of 23 August 1993. The agency was formed to enlighten the public on government policies, programmes and activities. It also has the responsibility of mobilising favourable public opinion and support for government policies, programmes and activities which will establish feedback channels to the government on all aspects of Nigerian national life. It also arouses the consciousness of all categories of Nigerians to their rights and privileges, responsibilities and obligations as citizens of Nigeria. Other duties of NOA are: to propagate and promote the spirit of dignity of labour, honesty and commitment to qualitative production, promotion and consumption of home produced commodities and services; and educate people on the need to eschew all vices in public life including corruption, dishonesty, electoral and census malpractice, ethnic parochial and religious bigotry, among others. Meanwhile, it is noteworthy that the mission of NOA is to consistently raise awareness, provide timely and credible feedback; positively change attitudes, values and behaviours; accurately and adequately inform; and sufficiently mobilise citizens to act in ways that promote peace, harmony; and national development. The agency has over 5,000 staff spanning across 36 states of the federation including the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and the 774 local government offices with over 15 platforms tailored to reach the highest number of Nigerians using its three major segmentation approach (NOA, 2022).

Most of the national issues can be resolved amicably without any rancour with transparent governance and positive policy implementations since such are easily generated based on feelings of deceptions and favouritism. Among the Key National Issues confronting the governments includes high rate of unemployment, and the potential for evictions and continued economic disruption in tourism, Police brutality Corruption, Insecurity, Drug abuse, The Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic, Corruption in Nigeria and Insecurity. National issues have both objective and subjective underpinning. The objective connotation is the condition itself, while the subjective is the belief that the situation would change. According to Julian (2019) this has to do with evolution of societal values. The structural functionalists, typified by Merton (1968) and Nisbet (1969) concluded that significant discrepancy between national standard and national reality has always been the genesis of National Issues. This discrepancy becomes manifest when one society or region felt their recognition are threatened. Thus, National Issues emanate from perceived sharp fall in the expected standards which may threaten the foundation of such society. Nigeria as one of the emerging user-countries of social media worldwide has witnessed people relying on information posted on social media on key national issues without checking the reliability of their sources (Alarape et al., 2022) sharing such information on social media has led to religious crises, political imbroglio, hate speech, racial discrimination and clashes, and a degenerated socio-psychological wellbeing of the citizens. This research was able to establish the credibility level of NOA the agency that was established to educate and equip the citizens with the knowledge of happenings in the country to discern reliable and dependable sources of information and to boost their loyalty to the citizen.

Statement of the problem

It is a generally known fact that Nigeria as a country is plagued with so many national issues. Meanwhile, it seems some of these issues are not clear to the general populace thereby leading to a high rate of misconception, panic and uncertainty. To worsen the situation, there are some conspirators who deliberately use social media to disseminating fake information about the key national issues mostly to discredit the government in power. Sensitising the public about these issues to clear the cloud, avert the dangers of ignorance, misconception, panic and uncertainty is imperatively important. Information must be passed across to the public to keep the general populace informed about the happenings in the society regarding the National Issues, so that precautionary measures can be strictly adhered to. National Orientation Agency (NOA) was established to serve as bridge between government and the public; create, build and sustain a good and favourable relationship; facilitates the goodwill of the public; and ensuring a seamless communication between the government and the public (NOA). It is therefore imperative to evaluate the roles of the agency (NOA) charged with the responsibility of communicating, educating and sensitising the public on key national issues on behalf of the government, hence, the study.

Research objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the extent to which National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on key national issues;
2. identify the media(s) through which the sensitisation programmes are being carried out; and
3. assess the level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes by the target publics.

Research questions

Arising from the concern of this study as stated above, three research questions were raised thus:

1. To what extent has the National Orientation Agency been sensitising the public on key national issues?

2. What are the media channels through which the National Orientation Agency carries the sensitisation programmes?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes by the target publics?

Review of related literature

Nigeria has experienced several crises due to content generated by social media, which mostly stems from speculation and conjecture on important national issues. Structural functionalists, typified by Merton (1968) and Nisbet (1969), argued that a national problem exists whenever there is a significant difference between the national norm and national reality. This conflict emerges when a region feels that its needs are not being met or are being threatened. National issues are usually not an accident, because in most cases they are deeply rooted in a society that has neglected certain basic needs. In short, national problems arise from disruptions in expected norms that can threaten the fabric of society. Nigeria's major national problems include:

The Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic: The coronavirus (COVID-19), an infectious disease that causes respiratory infections ranging from flu to more severe respiratory problems originated in the Hunan fish market in Wuhan, China, where live bats, snakes, raccoons and wild animals were sold in December 2019 (Shereen et al., 2020). The World Health Organisation (WHO) declared COVID-19 a pandemic on March 11, 2020, and since its identification, the virus has reportedly caused approximately 512,311 deaths worldwide out of total swooping number of 10,514, 028 infected persons globally, which unfortunately grows exponentially every day (WHO, 2020). In Nigeria, the government, organisations, agencies and wealthy citizens continue to make efforts to contain the spread of the disease after the first case was reported in the country on February 27, 2020. The Nigerian government (federal and state government) isolation centres and specialised health facilities to control the disease in collaboration with the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC). The government has also established a Presidential Task Force to monitor, obtain funds/support from private and corporate organisations and work closely with NCDC in line with international best practices. Part of the committee's mission is to communicate with citizens about measures being taken to contain the virus and to advise the federal government on public health issues. As these efforts continued, information spread unhindered across traditional and social media platforms at an astonishing rate. Both the consequences of the disease and the lack of information related to it have allowed medical misinformation to increase and spread rapidly on various social media.

Police Brutality: In 2020, a nationwide protest called on the Nigerian government to end police brutality and disband a violent police force known as the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS). Authorities have also taken steps to promote justice and accountability for police misconduct. Security forces and armed thugs harassed and attacked protesters in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory and some states. On October 20, footage on social media of men identified as militants called for shooting at peaceful protesters in Lagos. Several people are known to have died, but the death toll remains uncertain. The latest in this unfortunate situation was the killing of a pregnant lawyer on December 25, 2022, when she and her family were on their way from church along Ajah/Lekki Road in Lagos State. **Corruption in Nigeria:** Corruption has become a threat to economic sectors in Nigeria. The problem of corruption has recently reached dangerous proportions in Nigeria, so much so that it is widely believed that if something drastic is not done, it could lead to a total collapse of morals and ultimately the country's system. Ibraheem (2020) defines a situation where satisfaction is demanded or offered and accepted before the performance of official duties for which satisfaction should not be received otherwise. Corruption is an immoral activity, especially offering and accepting bribes. In Nigeria, corruption manifests itself in all aspects of public service, even in the judiciary. Nigerian citizens have known this for a long time. Police

officers openly and routinely extort money from drivers, commuters and passers-by without regard for the laws they are paid to enforce, while civil servants demand money before they can perform their duties. Garner (2014) considered corruption in two ways: first, as wickedness, perversion or violation, damage to integrity, virtue or moral principle, especially damage to the commitment of a public official through bribery. Second, corruption is an act intended to give an advantage that is incompatible with official duties and other rights.

Insecurity: Insecurity in the country continued as Boko Haram and its splinter group Islamic State in West Africa Province (ISWAP) continued to attack civilian, humanitarian and military targets. In attacks in April, suspected ISWAP militants burned the premises of three international aid organizations in Damasak, Borno state. More than a dozen were injured, eight died, and approximately 65,000 people were displaced (World Report, 2022). August 2, 1999, sixteen days after IDPs were returned to Kukawa Local Area on 18 August 1999, insurgents attacked the community and kidnapped at least 100 people. The government continued to forcefully return Nigerian refugees from Cameroon (National Emergency Management Agency, 1999).

Unemployment in Nigeria: It has become a major concern for significant stakeholders. According to Kester and Aderinoye (2020), out of millions unemployed youth, approximately 23 million are graduates with missing and insufficient skills and qualifications. Statista (2020) also stated that unemployment is one of the main national problems that must be addressed. This is probably the most damaging problem in Nigeria. The youth of this nation are predominantly working class and face the prospect of not being able to find work after spending their wealth on education. Even those who do not want to depend on white-collar workers do not have or do not have the necessary capital to start their own business. It always works and makes them more or less "educated illiterates". Second, more often than not, government policies are ill-motivated or misdirected because the national allegiance is that of the state or local government. Certain policies often favour some groups and undermine others. Rather than objective, tribal sentiments are needlessly shared. Another problem with the Nigerian situation is the problem of leadership. Most of the leaders of many Nigerian governments have not dealt with the problem of unemployment with dignity, thus the unemployed have resorted to anti-social threats such as armed robbery, burglars, fraudsters (419) get rich quick syndrome of able-bodied youths and educated but could not obtain legitimate prestige and dignified employment. Unemployed graduates are also involved in kidnapping for ransom, banditry and terrorism. High inflation and economic recession accelerate the growth of the unemployment rate; rampant economic growth, population explosion and the greed of leaders leading to high levels of corruption.

Poverty as a Social Problem: Poverty can also be considered as living below a certain minimum level. The official definition of public assistance benefits (1966) was "the level of resources at which a person is entitled to additional benefits". Adeboyade (1984) defined poor Nigerians as destitute, beggars and the disabled with no visible means of sustainable livelihood, single unemployed, homeless wandering families and social deviants living precariously on the fringes of society. Much of the deviant behaviour of society, such as the crime of immorality, divorce, alcoholism, drug addiction, and other crimes, is often attributed to poverty. It is also widely believed that eliminating poverty from society will reduce the incidence and severity of these social ills. Meanwhile, the 2022 World Bank Nigeria Poverty Assessment Report noted that slow economic growth, low human capital, labour market weaknesses and exposure to shocks hamper poverty in Nigeria. This report was mainly based on the 2018/2019 Nigeria Living Standard Survey (NLSS, 2019).

Religious Intolerance: Religion has been described as the cultural starting point of a nation's belief system. Belief systems can cause significant differences in personality and other character traits between individuals. Some are inevitably more committed to their beliefs and practices than others. In other words, some people may be weak and fail in the practice of their religion. Others, who think they are strong in faith, following the rules of the religious game, naturally feel offended

by the religious behaviour of the weaker. This can lead to religious intolerance even between members of the same religion. Religious intolerance therefore means the inability of some people, whether individuals or groups, to tolerate the weak or deviant behaviour of other members. It can also mean the inability of members of one religious group to tolerate the practices of another religious group. Such intolerance can easily lead to tension and disagreement, and my result is open confrontation

Meanwhile, the development in technology has made social media a convenient mechanism for spreading false or personally tailored contents, particularly during times of public tension like the current Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, Police brutality, Corruption, Insecurity, mass unemployment kidnapping and banditry (Zarocostas, 2020). Of recent, it is clear that the usage of social media platforms for misinformation is evident amongst the populace. In addition, the most noticeable features of social media characteristics is the seeming freedom that comes with the use of social media to the extent that users do no longer wait for the government to make official statements before spreading the uninformed information. Nigerians use various social media platforms such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Facebook, blogs to access, provide and to share information about the key national issues like the presence of corona virus, re-occurrence of banditry, Boko Haram insurgence, kidnapping and communal clash or attack in some part of the country. A day hardly goes by without the emergence of or a new case of some or all of these above mentioned key national issues, the development that gives rise to the use of social media platforms to provide information about the issues.

These bits of information that are passed across are mostly assumptions cum speculations, which are disseminated to spread panic to other members of the citizenry. Social media's rapid rise is a loud, desperate, emerging attempt by people everywhere to connect with each other in the face of all the obstacles that modernity imposes. Social media refers to the means of interactions among people in which they create, share, and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. Kaplan and Haenle (2012) defined social media as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2. 0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content." It introduces substantial and pervasive changes to communication between organisations, communities and individuals.

In retrospect, social media has not only been a platform for news and information dissemination, but has proved also a means of spreading panic, fear and confusion by the people to the people about the national key issues. This is largely possible because the use of social media is permissible to all and sundry, hence unverified and fake news can be passed on without fear or favour. Savrum and Leon (2015) asserted that "the media provide a freedom of choice and individuals are free to choose which broadcast best represents their interest." They further posited that the media exacerbates social issues thereby heightening negative impressions on these situations (Savrum & Leon, 2015). In view of the assertions, the advantages of social media cannot be too stressed as it crippled unpopular regimes and opened spaces for people to express their grievances albeit via virtual public spaces. However, when social media is negatively deployed, the uninformed easily fall prey to misinformation which at times brings mishap and confusion to the populace simply because social media is permissible to all and sundry, hence unverified and fake news are passed on without fear or favour and almost unchecked.

Notably, with the high rate of misconception, rumours mongering, panic and uncertainty, there is need to evaluate the roles and capability of the National Orientation Agency in containing, correcting the impression of the public, mediating between government and the citizens. This can be majorly done in terms of informing, educating and allaying the fear of the masses in order to stem the spread of misconception, rumours mongering, panic and uncertainty and ensure that the members of public have access to genuine and true situation about key National Issues. Therefore, sensitising the public about the key national issues, information must be passed across to keep the populace informed, educated and kept abreast of the key national issues and happening in the

society. Thus, it is believed that through information dissemination, more knowledge will be acquired about the various contending issues in the country and safety protocols to stem the spread of unfounded rumours in Nigeria. Observably, failure to educate the ignorant or uninformed public about the key national issues can wreck much havoc on the administration of government in power.

Considering the roles of National Orientation Agency in Nigerian political administration, one can aver that public relations is an aspect that cannot be ignored in governance in order to run an hitch-free administration and to educate members of the public about the happenings in the country. The Nigerian government established the National Orientation Agency (NOA) in order to serve as a bridge between it and the general public. From the above, it is clear that the country is experiencing series of crises spur by failure to educate the uninformed public about the key national issues which thereby popularise assumptions cum speculations which are disseminated and spread panic to other members of the country. It is therefore imperative to evaluate the roles of the agency (NOA) charged with responsibility of connecting with the masses on behalf of the government, hence, the study.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. The population consisted of 3,881,280 residents in the State of Osun (Population City, 2015). Multi stage sampling procedure and stratified sampling technique were used to select 810 respondents. The first stage involved the selection of the three senatorial districts and then using simple random sampling technique in selecting three local government areas from each of the senatorial district. At the second stage, the town that serves as the seat of the local governments were purposively selected thereby having nine towns. At the third stage, the population was stratified into educated and non-educated, civil servants and self-employed workers, rural dwellers and urban dwellers in order to have a fair representation of every members of the populace.

Fifteen (15) respondents each were then selected from these stratified groups using convenient sampling technique. A self-developed Questionnaire titled “Assessment of the National Orientation Agency (NOA) Public Relations Roles on Key National Issues Questionnaire (ANOAPRRKNIQ)” was used to collect data. The questionnaire comprised three (3) main sections based on the 3 questions the research intends to answer. Section A contains questions on the extent to which the National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on key national issues. Section B contains questions on the channel through which the National Orientation Agency carry the sensitisation programmes Section C contains questions on the level of acceptability of the National Orientation Agency sensitisation programmes by target publics on key national issues. Only 760 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved from the public respondents making 93.8% of the total sampled. In order to ensure the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach’s alpha, split half estimates were obtained from the SPSS 17 software. For the measure of value of the extent to which the National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on key national issues, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.839 was obtained. For the channel through which the National Orientation Agency carries the sensitisation programmes, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.901 was obtained. The questions on the level of acceptability of the National Orientation Agency sensitisation programmes by target publics on key national issues, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.796 was obtained. All these values indicated that the scales were very valid to measure the constructs they were purported to measure. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer the three research questions raised.

Data presentation and analysis

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on Key National Issues

Table 1: Extent to which National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on Key National Issues

	Variables	High extent	Moderate extent	Low extent	No extent	Mean	Decision
What is the level of public awareness of key National Issues created through NOA on Key National Issues	COVID-19	200(26.33)	208(27.37)	250(46.05)	102(13.33)	2.52	Moderate extent
	Boko Haram	117(15.39)	100(13.16)	303(39.87)	250(32.89)	2.14	Low extent
	Justice Delay	118(15.53)	121(15.92)	300(39.47)	221(29.08)	2.18	Low extent
	Religious Intolerance	60(7.89)	104(13.68)	290(38.16)	306(40.26)	1.89	Low extent
	Poverty	103(13.55)	170(22.37)	280(36.84)	307(40.39)	2.35	Low extent
	Unemployment	107(14.08)	80(10.53)	271(35.66)	302(39.74)	2.10	Low extent
	Insecurity	155(20.39)	170(22.37)	130(17.11)	305(40.13)	2.23	Low extent
	Corruption in Nigeria	90(11.84)	55(7.24)	450(59.21)	165(21.71)	2.09	Low extent
	Police Brutality	102(13.42)	108(14.21)	310(40.79)	230(30.26)	2.02	Low extent
	Weighted Mean =					2.16	Low extent

Source: Field Survey by Researchers, 2022

Table 1 shows the extent to which National Orientation Agency has been sensitising the public on Key National Issues presented in frequencies and percentages. Setting the decision rule to be ≥ 2.50 as Positive (High Extent) and ≤ 2.49 as Negative (Low Extent). The only national issue that the respondents attested to have a moderate extent of sensitisation courtesy of NOA is COVID-19 with Mean 2.53 of four-point Likert scale. Respondents attested that sensitization messages and information on Boko Haram with Mean 2.14 of four-point Likert Scale; Justice Delay, Mean 2.18 of four-point Likert Scale; Religious Intolerance with Mean 1.89 of four-point Likert Scale; Poverty with Mean 2.35 of four-point Likert Scale; Unemployment with Mean 2.10 of four-point Likert Scale; Insecurity with Mean 2.23 of four-point Likert Scale; Corruption in Nigeria with Mean 2.09 of four-point Likert Scale and Police brutality with Mean 2.02 of four-point Likert Scale failed the acceptable level of extent of public sensitisation on key national issues courtesy of NOA. The overall mean level of extent of sensitisation on key national issues is 2.16 failed the acceptable level of extent of sensitisation. The implication of this is that the presence of NOA is of low extent and not well notice for all the critical key national issues except COVID-19 that has moderate extent of sensitisation.

Research Question 2: What are the media with which respondents heard the sensitisation programmes on key national issues by National Orientation Agency

Table 2: Media channels through which respondents heard of the sensitisation programmes on key national issues by National Orientation Agency.

	Media of Communication	Frequency	Percentage
Media channels through which respondents are aware of NOA Programmes	Radio	305	40.14%
	Seminar	251	33.05%;
	TV	269	35.40%;
	Internet	385	50.66%;
	Newspaper	298	39.21%;
	Android phone	405	53.29%;
	Hand bill	259	34.11%.

Source: Field Survey by Researchers, 2022

Table 2 shows the media through which respondents heard the sensitisation programmes on key national issues from National Orientation Agency. 40.14% of those that got exposed to the sensitisation

on key National Issues from NOA heard it via a transistor radio; Seminar 33.05%; Television 35.40%; Internet, 50.66%; Newspaper 39.21%; Android phone 53.29%; and Hand bill 34.11%. The implication of this is that media of information were underutilised as Aggregate Weighted Mean of 2.35 of four-point Likert scale failed the acceptable level (2.5) of adequate utilisation of media of public sensitisation on key national issues courtesy of NOA

Research Question 3: What is the level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes by target publics?

Table 3: Level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes on key national issues by NOA

Items	Variables	Very desirable	Desirable	Undesirable	Very Undesirable	Mean	Decision
Do you believe that the information dished out or awareness made by NOA on Key National Issue is based on facts	COVID-19	190	146	264	160	2.22	Low
	Boko Haram	170	103	280	307	2.18	Low
	Justice Delay	107	80	271	302	1.99	Low
	Religious Intolerance	155	170	130	305	2.23	Low
	Poverty as a Social Problem	170	290	170	130	2.24	Low
	Unemployment	150	156	202	252	2.27	Low
	Insecurity	117	100	303	250	1.92	Low
	Corruption	189	121	250	210	2.16	Low
	Police Brutality	150	156	202	252	2.27	Low
	Aggregate Mean					2.16	Low
Do you agree that NOA did the most popular awareness in your community on the following key National	COVID-19	245	192	123	200	2.31	Low
	Boko Haram	152	180	221	207	2.21	Low
	Justice Delay	140	180	231	209	2.33	Low
	Religious Intolerance	155	196	214	195	2.41	Low
	Poverty as a Social Problem	200	183	240	137	2.29	Low
	Unemployment	126	189	245	200	2.32	Low
	Insecurity	180	151	290	199	2.39	Low
	Corruption	173	192	195	200	2.31	Low
	Police Brutality	152	187	200	221	2.36	Low
	Aggregate Mean					2.31	Low
Do you agree that NOA has improved people's knowledge about the prevalence of the following key	COVID-19	120	200	260	180	2.34	Low
	Boko Haram	60	180	200	220	2.37	Low
	Justice Delay	110	117	230	303	1.86	Low
	Religious Intolerance	167	142	249	200	2.40	Low
	Poverty as a Social Problem	106	171	280	203	2.24	Low
	Unemployment	163	202	245	145	2.34	Low
	Insecurity	160	208	189	203	2.30	Low
	Corruption	197	197	180	186	2.21	Low
	Police Brutality	167	103	245	245	2.18	Low
	Aggregate Mean					2.25	Low
How would you assess the effectiveness of NOA in enlightening the populace on the following key	COVID-19 b	150	164	196	250	2.28	Low
	Boko Haram	137	140	232	251	2.22	Low
	Justice Delay	189	145	206	220	2.39	Low
	Religious Intolerance	150	180	189	201	2.27	Low
	Poverty as a Social Problem	148	177	163	187	2.15	Low
	Unemployment	151	182	167	260	2.30	Low
	Insecurity	140	195	223	202	2.29	Low
	Corruption	152	187	221	200	2.33	Low
	Police Brutality	140	131	249	340	2.23	Low
	Weighted Mean					2.27	Low
OVERALL AGGREGATE MEAN						2.25	Low

Source: Field Survey by Researchers, 2022

From the table on the level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes on key national issues by NOA, the respondents that agreed that the information dished out and the awareness made

by NOA on Key National Issue is based on fact aggregate mean 2.16 fall below acceptable level of 2.50 and such has negative effect on acceptability of NOA and its programmes. On the issue of popularity of NOA sensitisation programmes on key national issues, respondents aggregated to mean 2.31 opined that her sensitisation programmes are popular also fall below acceptable level of 2.50 and such has negative effect on acceptability. Respondents, aggregate mean 2.25 attested that NOA has improved people's knowledge about the prevalence key national issues also fall below acceptable level of 2.50 and such has negative effect on acceptability. On the assessment of the effectiveness of NOA in enlightening the populace aggregate mean 2.27 of the respondents agreed that the NOA is effective, fall below acceptable level of 2.50 and such has negative effect on acceptability. However, the overall aggregate mean of 2.25 has fall below the acceptable level of 2.5 is an indication of a low level of acceptability of the sensitisation programmes of NOA. The four questions directed towards vivid explanation on level of acceptability of the NOA sensitisation programmes on key national issues were individually and collectively fall below the acceptable standard (2.5) an indication that the level of acceptability of the NOA sensitisation programmes is very low The low level of acceptability offers reason for apathy of people towards whatever activities and programmes NOA might have been dished out for the public consumption.

Conclusion

The research concluded that the NOA is ineffective in terms of carrying out its function properly and efficiently in Osun State. The respondents cast vote of no confidence on her as they presume most of the information dished out were mere propaganda to achieve one ulterior motives of the government she claim to represent. The vote of no confidence led to apathy on the part of the respondents towards whatever instruction, information or directives dished out by the agency. This justifies the assumption that public relations should be guided jealously in any organisation – either governmental or non-governmental. The cordial and mutually beneficial relationship an organisation builds and sustain with its publics will go a long way in ensuring that the mission and vision of the firm is achieved. The ineffectiveness that NOA has depicted during the trying period of key National issues has made her functions and responsibilities questionable. If something is not done, to salvage the situation, the agency might go into extinction or better still dissolved.

Recommendations

Since the presence of NOA is felt to a low extent and not well noticed in discussing the key national issues, it is therefore recommended that NOA should embark on awareness campaign and programmes that showcase the essence of her existence and creates several media through which people can get in touch. NOA has been adjudged to have underutilised media of information in sensitising the populace about the key National Issues and therefore recommended that NOA should employ information communication technology, social media platforms advantages to earnestly the interest and attention of the youth that constitute the majority of the population who at the same time are mostly affected by the said key national issues. Low level of acceptability of NOA metamorphosed into apartheid of people towards whatever programmes and information dished out for the public, it is recommended therefore that NOA needs the mission of rebuilding their image in order to regain the trust of the public.

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